

1 **PDE4B in embryonic stem cells and the trophectoderm.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
8 PDE4B as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells
9 of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Jin, S.L.C. and Conti, M., 2002. Induction of the cyclic nucleotide phosphodiesterase PDE4B is
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